

Synthesis, reactions, physicochemical characterization and biological studies of titanium(IV) Schiff base complexes

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Abstract : Some titanium(IV) complexes of the type $[\text{Ti}(\text{Cl})_{4-n}(\text{L})_n]$ (1-2), [where $n = 1$ or 2 , $\text{L} =$ Schiff bases; salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (LH)] have been synthesized by the reactions of titanium(IV) chloride with sodium salts of Schiff bases in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio(s) in $\text{MeOH-C}_6\text{H}_6$ respectively. Interaction of complex (1) with sodium salts of salicylidene-2-aminopyridine $[\text{Na}(\text{L}')]_2$, and tetraisopropoxyaluminate in equimolar ratio produces mixed ligand complex of the type; $[(\text{Cl})_2(\text{L})\text{Ti}(\text{L}')]_2$ (3) and bimetallic complex $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Ti}(\text{L})\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}]$ (4) respectively. Reaction of complex (3) with sodium isopropoxide yields the complex $[(\text{OPr}^i)_2(\text{L})\text{Ti}(\text{L}')]_2$ (5) in $\text{THF-C}_6\text{H}_6$ mixture. These complexes have been characterised by melting points, elemental analysis, and spectral [IR, NMR (^1H , ^{13}C), MS and Powder XRD] studies. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) curve shows multi-step decomposition with the formation of metal oxide residue. SEM analysis provides the morphology of the complexes. Antibacterial activity showing that the titanium(IV) complexes were found to be more potent than Schiff bases against some selected bacterial strains.

Keywords : Schiff bases, titanium(IV) complexes, ^1H , ^{13}C NMR, Mass, TGA, SEM, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Schiff bases have been considered as one of the most potential group of chelators for facile preparation of metallo-organic hybrid material. Much attention has been drawn towards the geometry of titanium(IV) metal complexes with Schiff bases showing coordination number(s) 5, 6, 7, and 8 around metal ion¹⁻⁷. There is continuing interest in metal complexes of Schiff bases containing Oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms in the backbones of these ligands. Group '4' metal complexes bearing the bidentate salicylaldehyde chelate ligands show extremely high catalytic (where Y is N or S) activity⁸ in α -olefin and ring opening polymerization of cyclic esters⁹ and antitumor¹⁰ as well as antimicrobial activity¹¹. A number of transition metal complexes as well as main group metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde have been synthesized and characterized in our laboratory¹²⁻¹⁷. As an extension of these studies, titanium(IV) complexes have been synthesized and characterized in during present course of investigation. The synthesized

ligands and metal complexes have been screened by antibacterial evaluation. The antibacterial results show that metal complexes found to be more potent.

Results and discussion

Titanium(IV) complexes (1-2) have been synthesized by the reactions of titanium tetrachloride with sodium salts of salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene $[\text{Na}(\text{L})]$ in the presence of $\text{MeOH-C}_6\text{H}_6$ mixture in different molar ratio(s), shown in Scheme 1, whereas the complex (1) has been treated with sodium salts of salicylidene-2-aminopyridine $[\text{Na}(\text{L}')]_2$ and tetraisopropoxyaluminate $[\text{Na}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}]$ in equimolar ratio to produce new mixed ligand complexes (3) and (4) respectively (Scheme 1).

The interaction of complex (3) with sodium isopropoxide $[\text{Na}(\text{OPr}^i)]$ yielded $[(\text{OPr}^i)_2(\text{L})\text{Ti}(\text{L}')]_2$ (5) in 1 : 2 molar ratio in $\text{THF-C}_6\text{H}_6$ mixture in Scheme 1.

All these complexes are coloured solid and soluble in polar organic solvents such as DMSO, DMF, THF, pyridine, methanol and ethanol.

Scheme 1. Synthesis and reactions of titanium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio(s).

Infrared spectra :

The IR spectra of the Schiff bases showed absorption band in the range ~ 1630–1625 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{(C=N)}}$ which get shifted to bathochromic shift¹² at 1614–1600 cm^{-1} on complexation (Table 1), indicate the involvement of

azomethine nitrogen to titanium, confirmed by the band at 456–448 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{(Ti←N)}}$ vibration. The disappearance of $\nu_{\text{(O-H)}}$ stretching band in the complexes with respect to Schiff bases observed at 3410–3360 cm^{-1} , suggests the deprotonation of phenolic proton via M–O bond

Table 1. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of titanium(IV) complexes containing Schiff bases

Sl. no.	Complex	$\nu_{\text{(C=N)}}$	$\nu_{\text{(C-O)}}$	$\nu_{\text{(M-O)}}$	$\nu_{\text{(M←N)}}$	$\nu_{\text{(M-Cl)ter}}$	$\nu_{\text{(M-Cl)br}}$	$\nu_{\text{(Al-O)}}$	$\nu_{\text{(C-O).Ti}}$
1.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{Cl})_4(\text{L})_2]$ (1)	1612	1282	546	455	345	247	–	–
2.	$[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Ti}(\text{L})_2]$ (2)	1609	1285	540	454	340	–	–	–
3.	$[(\text{Cl})_2(\text{L})\text{Ti}(\text{L}')]]$ (3)	1600	1286	527	451	340	–	–	–
4.	$[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Ti}(\text{L})\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}]$ (4)	1605	1280	510	450	341	–	597	1148 _{ter} 973 _{br}
5.	$[(\text{OPr}^i)_2(\text{L})\text{Ti}(\text{L}')]]$ (5)	1607	1289	523	448	343	–	–	1143 _{ter}

formation which is further supported by upward shifting¹ of the $\nu_{(C-O)}$ phenolic band at 1294–1280 cm^{-1} and appearance of band at 546–510 cm^{-1} due to M–O stretching vibration. Complex (1) exhibits band at 247 cm^{-1} have been assigned to the bridging $\nu_{(Ti-Cl)}$ vibration^{18,19} with an additional band observed at 345 cm^{-1} for terminal $\nu_{(Ti-Cl)}$ vibration^{1,15}, this fact has been further supported by FAB-MS spectrum showing dimeric nature of the complex. The complex (4) exhibited new bands to the metal alkoxide group $\nu_{(C-O)_Ti}$ at 1148 cm^{-1} for terminal isopropoxy group and at 973 cm^{-1} for bridging isopropoxy group¹⁴; beside these, a band observed at 597 cm^{-1} has been assigned²⁰ to $\nu_{(Al-O)}$.

NMR spectra :

A strong ¹H NMR signal at 12.80–12.40 ppm appeared in the Schiff base ligands due to phenolic proton (OH), whereas this signal was disappeared¹⁷ in the titanium(IV) complexes which is the indicative of coordination to metal through phenolic oxygen after deprotonation of phenolic proton. The azomethine proton deshielded at 8.82–9.49 ppm (Table 2) in the complexes suggesting the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in the coordination¹. Aromatic protons at 6.50–7.85 ppm in ligands, shifted slightly downfield upon coordination in the range 6.50–8.10 ppm.

In ¹³C NMR spectra, the signal at 158.91–157.50 ppm was attributed to the azomethine carbon (HC=N) in the Schiff bases which shifted upfield¹⁷ at 154.62–160.97 ppm in the complexes (Table 2), indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to titanium. The chemical shift value at 151.54–149.72 ppm in the Schiff bases was shifted downfield at 161.12–163.63 ppm in the complexes suggesting the bonding of phenolic oxygen^{12,17} to the metal via M–O bond formation. The representative spectra of ¹H and ¹³C NMR are given in Figs. 1 and 2.

Mass spectra :

The FAB-mass spectrum of the complex $[(\mu-Cl)_2Ti_2(Cl)_4(L)_2]$ (1) showed a characteristic molecular ion peak (Fig. 3) at m/z 727 (23%) $[(C_{28}H_{24}N_2O_2Ti_2Cl_6)]$; calculated mass = 726 based on ³⁵Cl and ⁴⁸Ti] which supports to the molecular mass of the complex in a dimeric structure^{12,15}. Several peaks were also observed in mass spectrum at m/z 711 (26.2%), 676 (24.9%), 573 (28.3%), 482 (17.7%), 412 (39%), 385 (11.4%), 309 (31.1%) and 210 (100%) due to successive fragmentation (Scheme 2) of complex in different pathway. ESI-mass spectrum of complexes $[(Cl)_2Ti(L)_2]$ (2) (Fig. 4) showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 538.2156 (7.6%) $[(C_{28}H_{24}N_2O_2TiCl_2)]$; calculated mass = 538 based on ³⁵Cl and ⁴⁸Ti] corresponding to proposed formula^{17,21} in monomeric composition. The spectrum of complex (2) exhibited prominent peaks¹⁷ at m/z 420 (1.1%), 315 (6.8%), 245 (1.3%), 210 (100%) and 156 (1.5%) due to fragmentation of molecule (Scheme 3). The base peak was observed at m/z 210, represents $[C_6H_4OCl_2Ti]$ species due to isotopic distribution in the complex (1) and (2).

Thermogravimetric analysis :

The % weight loss of the complexes was measured in multi-steps^{22,23} shown in TGA curve in the form of non-horizontal lines (downwards) (Fig. 5) regarded as multiple events due to organic pyrolysis leaving to metal oxide residue. Complex (1) degrades in to four steps. The molecular mass of the complex (1) is 726 and the total weight loss of the complex was found to be 70.9801%. The residue of the complex is 29.019% which is equal to approximate mass of the complex 210 (28.927%) due to $[C_6H_5Cl_2OTi]$ remaining material. First degradation occurs within a range 55–180 °C due to some organic part of ligand $[C_8H_8NCl]$ has lost. In second step of weight loss, remaining part further decomposed due to loss of

Table 2. NMR data (ppm) for the titanium(IV) Schiff base complexes

Complex	¹ H NMR			¹³ C NMR			
	(ArCH ₃) (s)	HC=N (s)	ArH (m)	(C=N) (s)	(C-O) (s)	(ArCH ₃) (s)	(ArC) (m)
$[(\mu-Cl)_2Ti_2(Cl)_4(L)_2]$ (1)	2.50	8.86	6.50–7.67	158.53	162.87	17.85	118.12–147.00
$[(Cl)_2Ti(L)_2]$ (2)	2.35	8.82	6.78–7.64	160.97	163.63	18.29	118.70–137.86
$[(Cl)_2(L)Ti(L')]$ (3)	2.32	8.95	6.81–8.05	156.79	163.28	17.94	116.31–148.73

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of complex [(μ-Cl)₂Ti₂(Cl)₄(L)₂] (1).

Fig. 2. ¹³C NMR spectrum of complex [(μ-Cl)₂Ti₂(Cl)₄(L)₂] (1).

C₇H₇ moiety in the range 210–320 °C. The third step weight loss (13.223%) in the range 350–510 °C due to elimination of HCN, Cl₂, followed by fourth decomposition in the temperature range 530–740 °C due to removal of C₆H₄, TiOCl and reaches to the formation of

[C₆H₅Cl₂O₂Ti] species as final decomposition material. The final decomposition product is also confirmed by remaining material percentage 29.019 (28.927).

PXRD and SEM studies :

Powder X-ray diffraction pattern of complexes (1) and

Fig. 3. FAB-mass spectrum of complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{Cl})_4(\text{L})_2]$ (**1**).

Scheme 2. Mass fragmentation pattern of complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{Cl})_4(\text{L})_2]$ (**1**).

Fig. 4. ESI-mass spectrum of complex $[(Cl)_2Ti(L)_2]$ (2).

Scheme 3. Mass fragmentation pattern of complex $[(Cl)_2Ti(L)_2]$ (2).

(3) is shown in Figs. 6 and 7, reveals that the complexes exhibit sharp peaks indicating crystalline nature of the complexes. From XRD patterns, the particle size for the complexes (1) and (3) was estimated²⁴ by using Debye Scherrer formula are 68 nm and 54 nm, respectively. The surface morphology of the complexes was studied by

using SEM. The non uniform matrix was observed in the Schiff base metal complexes, shown in Fig. 8. From the SEM images, the complexes (1), (2) and (4) show the granular shaped morphology with the particle size of 68 nm, platelet like morphology and closed packed agglomerated morphology with average size less than 1 μ m,

Fig. 5. TGA curve of the complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{Cl})_4(\text{L})_2]$ (1).

Fig. 6. Powder X-ray diffraction pattern of complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{Cl})_4(\text{L})_2]$ (1).

Fig. 7. Powder X-ray diffraction pattern of complex $[(\text{Cl})_2(\text{L})\text{Ti}(\text{L}')]$ (3).

respectively. However, particle sizes less than 100 nm were also observed that groups to form agglomerates of larger size^{24,25}.

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activity of free Schiff bases and titanium(IV) complexes has been evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus* (G^+), *Escherichia coli* (G^-) and

Pseudomonas aeruginosa (G^-). The results of antibacterial activities are presented at concentration 50, 100 and 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in Table 3.

(i) Schiff bases are equal or highly active in comparison to chloramphenicol. HL' is highly active against *S. aureus*.

(ii) The tested complexes have greater activity¹³ than

Fig. 8. SEM images of titanium(IV) complexes : (a) $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{Cl})_4(\text{L})_2]$ (1), (b) $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Ti}(\text{L})_2]$ (2), (c) $[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Ti}(\text{L})\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}]$ (4).

Table 3. Antibacterial activity results of inhibition zone (mm)

Complex	Bacterial concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)								
	<i>S. aureus</i> (G^+)			<i>E. coli</i> (G^-)			<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (G^-)		
	50	100	200	50	100	200	50	100	200
HL	+	+	++	+	+	++	+	+	+
HL'	+	++	+++	+	+	++	+	++	++
$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{Cl})_4(\text{L})_2]$ (1)	++	+++	++++	+	++	+++	+	++	+++
$[(\text{Cl})_2\text{Ti}(\text{L})_2]$ (2)	+	++	++	+	++	++	+	++	+++
$[(\text{Cl})_2(\text{L})\text{Ti}(\text{L}')]$ (3)	++	+++	++++	++	++	+++	++	+++	++++
$[(\text{OPr}^i)_2(\text{L})\text{Ti}(\text{L}')]$ (5)	+	++	+++	+	++	++	+	+++	+++
S	+	+	++	+	+	++	+	++	++

Well diameter 6 mm, inhibition values beyond control are + = 1-5 mm, ++ = 6-10 mm, +++ = 11-15 mm, ++++ = 16-20, and S = standard (Chloramphenicol).

Schiff bases and standard chloramphenicol against tested bacteria.

(iii) Complex (1) is highly active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* than complex (2).

(iv) Complex (3) exhibited better antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* than complex (2) indicating heterocyclic pyridine moiety.

The remarkable antibacterial results showed that the titanium(IV) complexes are effective potential as antibacterial agents in comparison to Schiff bases against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, is explained on the theory of chelation²⁶.

Experimental

Materials and measurements :

All glass apparatus with standard joints were used throughout the experimental procedure. Stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Solvents were dried before use according to standard literature procedure²⁷.

Aluminium isopropoxide was prepared and estimated gravimetrically as aluminium oxinate²⁸. Isopropanol was estimated²⁰ by oxidation with normal $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution in 12.5% H_2SO_4 . Titanium was estimated gravimetrically as its oxide. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were performed on a Heraceous Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. Titanium tetrachloride (Merck), 2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (Merck), 2-aminopyridine (Merck) and salicylaldehyde (Loba) were used as such. The infrared spectra of ligands and the complexes, in the range $4000\text{-}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, were recorded in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 1000 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer. The FAB-mass spectrum was recorded on JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. ESI-mass spectra were recorded on WATERS-HAB 213 spectrometer. Thermogravimetric (TG) analysis was carried out on Mettler Toledo with heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

min⁻¹. SEM images were recorded from Nanosciences, IIT, Kanpur. The X-ray powder diffraction was recorded on Rigaku model D/Max-2200 PC with Cu-K α_1 radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$).

Synthesis of ligands :

The Schiff bases (LH), salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (LH) and salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (L'H) were prepared by using equimolar amounts of salicylaldehyde and 2-methyl-1-aminobenzene/2-aminopyridine in methanol as reported^{12,17}. Further, sodium salts, [Na(L)] and [Na(L')] were prepared by dissolving equimolar amounts of sodium metal and salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene and salicylidene-2-aminopyridine in methanol, whereas sodium tetraalkoxyaluminate [Na{Al(OPrⁱ)₄}] prepared by standard literature procedure²⁹.

Synthesis of complexes :

[(μ -Cl)₂Ti₂(Cl)₄(L)₂] (1) : A freshly prepared sodium salt of salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (3.472 g, 14.9 mmol) in CH₃OH (~25 ml) was added to titanium(IV) chloride (2.842 g, 1.64 ml, 14.9 mmol) in C₆H₆ (~25 ml) in 1 : 1 molar ratio with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for ~4 h. The precipitated NaCl (0.849 g, 14.9 mmol) was removed by filtration followed by drying under reduced pressure to afford brick red coloured solid which was purified by recrystallization from methanol. Yield : (4.273 g, 79%), m.p. 180 °C (Found : C, 46.23; H, 3.27; N, 4.35; Ti, 13.18. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₄N₂O₂Cl₆Ti₂ : C, 46.28; H, 3.31; N, 4.41; Ti, 13.22%).

[(Cl)₂Ti(L)₂] (2) : Similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of complex (2) by interaction of titanium(IV) chloride and sodium salts of Schiff base in 1 : 2 molar ratio(s). Orange colour, yield : 81%, m.p., 183 °C (Found : C, 62.41; H, 4.40; N, 5.91; Ti, 8.88. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₄N₂O₂Cl₂Ti : C, 62.45; H, 4.46; N, 5.95; Ti, 8.92%).

[(Cl)₂(L)Ti(L')] (3) : Sodium salts of salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (0.906 g, 4.12 mmol) in THF (~20 ml) was added to the THF-C₆H₆ solution (~25 ml) of complex [(μ -Cl)₂Ti₂(Cl)₄(L)₂] (1) (1.502 g, 4.12 mmol) in equimolar ratio with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for ~4 h. The resulting brownish yellow coloured solution was filtered. The filtrate was

concentrated and dried under reduced pressure to afford brown coloured solid [(Cl)₂(L)Ti(L')] (3). Yield : (1.514 g, 70%), m.p. 180 °C (Found : C, 59.40; H, 3.96; N, 7.98; Ti, 9.07. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₁N₃O₂Cl₂Ti : C, 59.43; H, 4.00; N, 8.00; Ti, 9.14%).

[{(μ -OPrⁱ)₂Al(OPrⁱ)₂}Ti(Cl)₂(L)] (4) : Complex (1) (0.497 g, 1.37 mmol) in THF-C₆H₆ (~30 ml) solution was added to the sodium tetraisopropoxyaluminate (0.392 g, 1.37 mmol) in THF (~30 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred with refluxing for ~6 h. The light yellow coloured precipitate was filtered and dried under reduced pressure to afford yellow solid [{(μ -OPrⁱ)₂Al(OPrⁱ)₂}Ti(Cl)₂(L)] (4). Yield : (0.607 g, 75%), m.p. 190 °C (Found : C, 52.72; H, 6.70; N, 2.33; Ti, 8.10; Al, 4.49; OPrⁱ, 39.62. Calcd. for C₂₆H₄₀NO₅Cl₂TiAl : C, 52.79; H, 6.77; N, 2.37; Ti, 8.12; Al, 4.57; OPrⁱ, 39.93%).

[{(OPrⁱ)₂(L)Ti(L')] (5) : Complex (3) (0.50 g, 0.952 mmol) in THF-C₆H₆ (~30 ml) solution was added to the sodium isopropoxide (0.156 g, 1.90 mmol) in THF (~30 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred with refluxing for ~6 h. The light yellow coloured precipitate was filtered and dried under reduced pressure to afford brown solid. Yield : (0.794 g, 73%), m.p. 185 °C (Found : C, 66.92; H, 6.05; N, 7.02; Ti, 8.30; Al, 4.69; OPrⁱ, 20.42. Calcd. for C₃₂H₃₅N₃O₄Ti : C, 67.01; H, 6.11; N, 7.33; Ti, 8.37; Al, 4.71; OPrⁱ, 20.59%).

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activities of free ligand and titanium(IV) complexes have been screened *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus* (WHO 100) (G⁺), *Escherichia coli* (DH 5 alpha) (G⁻) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 1488) (G⁻) in DMSO by using the disc diffusion method¹⁴. The complexes dissolved in DMSO to get 200 μ g/ml solutions. Further progressive double dilution was performed to obtain the required concentration of 100 and 50 μ g/ml. About 0.5 ml (containing 10⁷ micro-organisms per ml) of investigated microorganisms was added to a sterile nutrient agar medium just before solidification, and then poured on sterile petri dishes and allowed to solidify. Using a sterile cork borer (6 mm in diameter), three holes (wells) were made in each disc and then 1 ml of tested complex dissolved in DMSO was poured in to these holes. Finally, the dishes were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Zones

of the inhibition of growth were measured in mm against bacteria. Chloramphenicol was used as positive control and DMSO was used as negative control. A blank containing only DMSO showed no inhibition on organisms in a preliminary test.

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